
New Terminologies among Millennials: Upshot of Coinage

Gilda E. Deguma, Ed.D.¹, Divine Grace B. Magtiza, Mat²

¹Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College Main Campus, Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines

²Estancia National High School, Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines

ABSTRACT: This descriptive research aimed to determine the use of new terminologies among millennials as the upshot of coinage in the municipality of Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines for the year 2017-2018. The 150 purposively-selected participants were classified as to gender, profession, generation, and area of residence. A 60-item researcher-made questionnaire and three interview questions were utilized. The statistical data gathered were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha, deviation all set at 0.05 level of significance. When the participants were taken as an entire group, they mostly used the new terminologies "occasionally". There was a significant difference in the use of new terminologies among participants and they revealed that the coinage was based on an experience or at an impulse; share new terminologies with friends and classmates or by social media; accepted the changes in the language because they believe that language is dynamic and as millennials; and considered this change as part of their generation.

KEYWORDS: New terminologies; Millennials; Coinage: Generation; Communication

I. INTRODUCTION

Words spread like weeds - seemingly at random but actually governed by an invisible force, and suddenly new ones are emerging from who knows where. The uncertain and gradual growth of words makes it nearly impossible to pinpoint where they started or how they caught on. But that is starting to change, as linguists draw on a wealth of data about word usage from social media services like Twitter (Sonnad, 2015).

Jack Grieve, a forensic linguist at Aston University in Birmingham, England, has been examining a dataset of nearly 9 billion tweeted words to identify the new American vocabulary. Identifying these words is interesting enough, but it doesn't tell us how they came to be. Grieve worked to visualize how these new words spread across the United States, using millions of tweets that had the user's location attached to them (Sonnad, 2015).

The transformations within a language take place on different levels of phonetic, morphemic, lexical, syntactic, etc. and the first three ones are the layers that are the most susceptible to change which may be evident even to one certain generation (Levchenko, 2010). All living systems change, and languages are no exception (Baron, 2000 in Magtiza, 2018) and English has always changed over time due to different kinds of influences. There were several historical incidents which determined its development such as the emergence of pidgins and creoles which is also responsible for changes of languages in general (Dietzel, 2007).

Coinage, according to Kosur (2012), is the word formation process in which a new word is created either deliberately or accidentally without using the other word formation processes and often from seemingly nothing. For example, the following list of words provides some common coinages found in everyday English: aspirin, escalator, heroin, band-aid, factoid, Frisbee, Google, kerosene, Kleenex, Laundromat, linoleum, muggle, nylon, psychedelic, Quark, Xerox, Zipper. Word-formation could be found in languages all over the world and English could be seen as the most important source for other languages in every respect and a huge amount of English terms spread like wildfire to other countries.

As dictionary publishers never tire of reminding us, our language is growing. Not content with the million or so words they already have at their disposal, English speakers are adding new ones at the rate of around 1,000 a year.

Recent dictionary debutants include blog, grok, crowdfunding, hackathon, airball, e-marketing, sudoku, twerk and Brexit. But these represent just a sliver of the tip of the iceberg. According to Global Language Monitor, around 5,400 new words are created every year; it's only the 1,000 or so deemed to be in sufficiently widespread use that made it into print (Bodle, 2016).

Every language is constantly turning into something different, and when we hear a new word or a new pronunciation or use of an old word, we may be catching the early stages of a change. Coinage is like fashion in clothing, hairstyles, cooking, entertainment, and government language that is constantly being revised or recreated (Algeo, 2000). Change is inevitable that language has its own train to trail and younger generations nowadays have their own system of language that the older generations sometimes cannot cope with them.

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In the latest quarterly update of Oxford English Dictionary (OED) has added approximately 500 words, phrases, and meanings to its lexicon. Three South African words are on this newest list. Connor Martin, in this update is said to contain dozens of items which are not recorded before the 21st century, but which are now widely used in English, including jeggings, photobomb, crowdfund, totes, staycation, and sext (Martin, 2014). Very roughly speaking, Dent (in Nordquist, 2019) said there are five primary contributors to the survival of a new word: usefulness, user-friendliness, exposure, the durability of the subject it describes, and its potential associations or extensions. If a new word fulfills these robust criteria it stands a very good chance of inclusion in the modern lexicon.

A study by Astrero (2017) emphasized that Philippine English has an informal variety, especially in the spoken mode, which may include a lot of borrowing and code-mixing, and it has a formal variety which, when used by educated speakers and found acceptable by educated Filipino circles, can be called Standard Philippine English. She added that the development of Philippine English has had its own particular history linked to the educational development of the Philippines under American colonial rule and that of the postcolonial era. The study also proved that technology is an effective vehicle for language disposal since the accessibility to reading materials, television, and internet are significant to the understanding of respondents to the lexemes of Philippine English. Despite the fact that the words were popular in 1960's, millennials reported a significant understanding to the words. This understanding was validated by being able to trace the evolution of the words and being able to identify new words popular today. The neologism in Philippine English is regarded by millennials as informal language.

This study was anchored on three theories: Generational Cohort Theory by Strauss and Howe, Onomasiological Theory by Pavol Štekauer and Social Network Theory by Brass. According to Strauss and Howe, Generation Cohort Theory attempted to follow each generation as a train in motion rather than as a station. With this, they trace the development of cohorts from childhood through death, marking the distinctive events which influence each group. The Onomasiological Theory, originally developed by Pavol Štekauer (2006), emphasizes the process of coining new naming units (words) which takes as its point of departure the naming needs of a speech community, and proceeds through conceptual reflection of extra-linguistic reality and semantic analysis to the form of a new naming unit. Its goal is to find the words that describe a given concept, idea, or object. Word-formation is conceived of as an independent component. With the constantly changing language, it is hard to keep track of new trends and tendencies that influence it on every-day basis. Since language is a flexible system of signs, it is its natural predisposition to be shaped and influenced by its users who are able to adopt it according to their will. On the other hand, Social network theory is a social science concept that discusses the connection and relationship in a social structure (Kadushin, 2004). According to Brass (1992), a social network is a generic way by a set of nodes (individuals or organizations) or actors who are connected by a set of social relationships, ties, or a specified type of ties by one or more specific types of interdependency, such as friendship, kinship, financial exchange, dislike, or relationships of beliefs, knowledge or prestige. Social network focuses on understanding how patterns of relationship connect individuals, people, groups or organizations generate opportunities and contexts for human behaviour.

This study was conducted to establish and measure the level of use of newly-created terminologies among millennials as upshot of coinage and how they shared and interpreted the terminologies online and in the real world which later became part of their language and eventually a trend of their generation, specifically in Estancia, Iloilo.

In today's generation, particularly in the municipality of Estancia, Iloilo, there is a lack of study about this particular topic, so the researchers conducted this research to contribute to the knowledge of locales especially students and professionals considered as millennials. This study also aimed to determine the level use of new terminologies among millennials as upshot of coinage for the year 2017-2018.

II. METHODS

A. *Research Design.*

This study used the descriptive design which deals with the present condition (de Belen, 2019). In relation, this study aimed to gain an understanding of the underlying reasons and opinions as it provides insights into the situation of the younger generations. It purposely described, explained, and validated the findings on the use of new terminologies as upshot of coinage among millennials. Interview among the participants was done to validate questions in this study.

B. *Participants.*

The participants were the 150 purposively-selected residents of Poblacion Zone 1, Zone 2, and Zone 3 of the municipality of Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines in the year 2017-2018. When classified as to gender, there were 55 (36.70%) male respondents, 73 (48.70%) female respondents, 14 (9.30%) homosexual respondents, and 8 (5.03%) lesbian respondents. When classified as to profession, there were 106 (70.70%) non-professional respondents, and 44 (29.30%) professional respondents. When classified as to generation,

87 (58.00%) were from generation Z and 63 (42.00%) from generation Y. When classified as to area of residence, there were 54 (36.00%) respondents from Zone I, 53 (35.30%) from Zone II, and 43 (28.70%) from Zone III. This study was conducted in 2017-2017 specifically in Zone I, Zone II, and Zone III of Estancia, Iloilo, Philippines. These selected areas have fast growing population

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and are at the center of the town's business and industry with lots of establishments and institutions arising. These include banks, schools, malls, stores, restaurants, recreational areas, convenient stores, pension houses, and many more. The graphical presentation is shown below.

C. Research Instruments.

The research instrument used was a researcher-made checklist which underwent validation by three jurors and reliability test by respondents in different places like schools and barangays who were not the actual respondents. The researcher-made checklist had (5) columns and the respondents checked how often they use the following coinages when they send text messages, send e-mails, and post messages in social media and ordinary conversations.

D. Data Gathering Procedure.

Prior to the conduct of the study, a letter was sent to experts for the validation of the researchersmade instrument. After which, the researchers sought the consent of the identified respondents who were purposively-selected from the three barangays of the municipality of Estancia. The researchers also identified few participants for interview for the triangulation of data. The data were submitted for data computation and analysis. The statistical tools used were Frequency Count and Percentage, Cronbach's Alpha, Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis H Test. Interview questions were also asked from the participants to validate the results of the study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Level of Use of Coined Terminologies among Millennials when Taken as an Entire Group

Table 1 shows the new terminologies as used by the millennials when taken as an entire group and how these words are used. Out of the 29 words listed, 13 were used occasionally, 12 were used sometime, 3 were used frequently, and 1 is used rarely. No words were used usually and every time. The participants were heterogeneously grouped on their level of use of coined terminologies with standard deviation range from 1.44 to 2.13.

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TABLE 1 . Level of Use of Coined Terminologies among Millennials when Taken as an Entire Group

Entire Group				Description
	Mean	SD	MD	
Jeggings	2.75	1.44	3.00	Occasionally
Photobomb	3.07	1.47	5.00	Occasionally
On-trend/Trending	3.77	1.81	4.00	Sometimes
On fleek	3.07	1.55	4.00	Occasionally
Slay/Bum	3.20	1.65	4.00	Occasionally
Woke	3.42	1.65	3.00	Occasionally
Internet	4.74	1.94	4.00	Frequently
Epic	3.86	1.82	4.00	Sometimes
Goals(BBF/Couple goals)	4.31	1.86	3.00	Sometimes
Swag	3.59	1.80	4.00	Sometimes
Cyberspace	3.18	1.80	3.00	Occasionally
Emoji	4.61	1.89	5.00	Frequently
App	4.53	2.00	4.00	Frequently
Vacay	3.77	1.70	4.00	Sometimes
Bruh/Bro	3.72	1.84	4.00	Sometimes
Goat	3.12	1.76	3.00	Occasionally
Basic	4.06	1.75	4.00	Sometimes
Bet	3.83	1.74	4.00	Sometimes
Netizens	4.00	2.02	4.00	Sometimes
Fo sho	2.79	1.71	2.50	Rarely
Perf	2.94	1.72	3.00	Occasionally
Groufie	4.04	1.90	4.00	Sometimes
Boyf/Boyfie	3.44	1.93	3.00	Occasionally
Sis/Sissy	3.82	1.83	4.00	Sometimes
Nope	3.93	1.83	4.00	Sometimes
Obvs	3.30	1.74	3.00	Sometimes
LMS	3.30	1.73	3.00	Sometimes
Whatevs	3.08	1.72	3.00	Occasionally
Sesh	3.37	1.83	3.00	Occasionally

Note: 1.00-1.86 Never, below 10%; 1.87-2.72 Rarely, 10%; 2.73-3.58 Occasionally, 30%; 3.59-4.44 Sometimes, 50%; 4.45-5.30 Frequently, 70%; 5.31-6.16 Usually, 90%; 6.17-7.00 Everytime, above 90%

B. Level of Use of Coined Terminologies among Millennials when Taken as an Entire Group

Table 2 shows that out of the 30 words listed, 15 were used occasionally and 15 were used sometimes. No words were used rarely, frequently, usually, and every time.

Table 2. Level of Use of Coined Terminologies among Millennials when Taken as an Entire Group

Entire Group				Description
	Mean	SD	MD	
D'oh/D'uh	3.00	1.63	3.00	Occasionally
Noob/JOJO	3.06	1.72	3.00	Occasionally
Matchy-matchy	3.39	1.90	3.00	Occasionally
Yaas	3.26	1.75	3.00	Occasionally
FOMO	3.41	1.75	3.00	Occasionally
YOLO	3.28	1.75	3.00	Occasionally
LB	3.37	1.78	3.00	Occasionally
TBT	3.96	1.88	4.00	Sometimes
OMG	3.76	1.72	4.00	Sometimes
OOTD	3.78	2.00	4.00	Sometimes
FL	3.87	1.90	4.00	Sometimes
NVM	3.87	2.03	4.00	Sometimes
LOL/ROFL	3.54	1.92	4.00	Sometimes
LMAO	3.65	1.88	4.00	Sometimes
BRB	3.93	2.08	3.00	Sometimes
TBH	3.90	1.99	3.00	Sometimes
AMIRITE	3.06	1.96	3.00	Occasionally
RN	2.87	1.81	3.00	Occasionally
IDC	3.37	1.96	3.00	Occasionally
IDK	3.76	2.03	3.00	Occasionally
IMYSM	3.43	1.74	3.00	Occasionally
TYL	3.43	1.83	3.00	Occasionally
CYL	3.51	1.82	3.00	Occasionally
WERPA	3.60	1.90	3.00	Sometimes
TGIF	3.66	1.88	3.00	Sometimes
HMUA	3.46	1.90	3.00	Occasionally
CTTO	3.62	1.90	3.00	Sometimes
PM	3.97	2.13	3.00	Sometimes
SS	4.07	2.01	4.00	Sometimes
BNW	3.66	1.86	4.00	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.86 Never, below 10%; 1.87-2.72 Rarely, 10%; 2.73-3.58 Occasionally, 30%; 3.59-4.44 Sometimes, 50%; 4.45-5.30 Frequently, 70%; 5.31-6.16 Usually, 90%; 6.17-7.00 Everytime, above 90%

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The result further shows that when the participants were classified as to gender, there was a statistically significant difference in the following coined terminologies: On trend/ Trending, Internet, Goals (BBF goals/couplegoals), Cyberspace, Emoji, App, Fo Sho, Perf, Sis, and TBT.

A Post-hoc analysis showed significant difference between Male and Homosexual with On trend/Trending, Internet, Epic, Emoji, App, Fo Sho, and Perf. Between Female and Homosexual the words were: On trend/Trending, Internet, Epic, Fo sho, and Perf, between Male and Female with Cyberspace and Sis/Sissy.

When classified as to area of residence, there was a statistically significant difference in the following coined terminologies: Epic, App, LB, OMG, OOTD, and NVM.

A Post-hoc analysis showed significant difference in the following coined terminologies: Between Zone 1 and Zone 2 the word was, Epic. For Zone 1 and 3 the words were: Epic, App, LB, OMG, NVM and OOTD. Between Zone 2 and 3 the words were: LB, OMG, OOTD, and NVM.

Further, when classified as to generation, there was no significant difference in the following coined terminologies between generation Y and generation Z: Jeggings, Photobomb, On-trend/Trending, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Internet, Epic, Goals (BBF/Couple goals), Swag, Cyberspace, Emoji, App, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Goat, Basic, Bet, Retweet, Netizens, Fo sho, Perf, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Obvs, LMS, Whatever Sesh, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, BRB, TBH, RN, IDK, IMYSM, TYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, PM and SS. On the other hand, there was a significant difference on the following words Nope, Noob, TBT, OMG, CTTO and BNW.

When classified as to profession, there was no significant difference in the following coined terminologies between professional and non-professional participants: Photobomb, On-Trend/Trending, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Internet, Epic, Cyberspace, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Goat, Bet, Retweet, Netizens, Fo sho, Perf, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy $U=2091.000$ $Z=-0.-$, Nope, Obvs, LMS, Whatever, D'oh/D'uh, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OMG, OOTD, LOL/ROFL, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, WERPA, TGIF, and HMUA. However, the following coined terminologies showed a significant difference: Goals (BBF/couple goals), Basic, Noob, NVM, LMAO, BRB, IDK, CYL, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW.

The findings of the study revealed that when the respondents were taken as an entire group the 150 respondents "occasionally" used the following coinages: Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Goat, Retweet, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Obvs, Whatever, Sesh, D'oh/D'uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, LOL/ROFL, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, TYL, CYL, and HMUA. While the following coinages were "sometimes" used: On-trend/Trending, Epic, Goals(BBF/Couple goals), Swag, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, TBT, OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LMAO, BRB, TBH, IDK, WERPA, TGIF, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW. The words Emoji, App, Internet were "frequently" used. The coinage Fo sho was "rarely" used.

When classified as to gender, the male participants used the coined words Jeggings and Fosho "rarely". The words, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Goat, Retweet, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Obvs, Whatever, Sesh, D'oh/D'uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, TYL, and HMUA were used "occasionally". On-trend/Trending, Epic, Goals (BBF/Couple goals), Swag, Cyberspace, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Nope, LMS, OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, IDK, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW were used "sometimes". Internet, Emoji, and App, were "frequently" used.

For the female participants, the words Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Swag, Cyberspace, Goat, Perf, Nope, Obvs, Whatever, Sesh, D'oh/D'uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, LMAO, LMS, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, TYL, WERPA, and HMUA were used "occasionally". The words On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Retweet, Netizens, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, BRB, IDK, CYL, TGIF, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW were "sometimes" used. The words Internet, Goals (BBF goals/ Couple goals), Emoji, and App were "frequently" used. Fo sho was "rarely" used.

For the homosexual participants, the coined word Jeggings was "rarely" used. The words Photobomb, Ontrend/ Trending, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Internet, Epic, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), Swag, Cyberspace, Emoji, App, Bruh/Bro, Goat, Retweet, Netizens, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, Obvs, Whatever, Sesh, D'oh/D'uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OMG, OOTD, FL, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IDK, TYL, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW were used "occasionally" used. Vacay, Basic, Bet, Fo sho, Perf, NVM and IMYSM were used "sometimes" used.

For the lesbian participants, coined words Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Epic, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), Swag, Bruh/Bro, Netizens, Whatever, and D'oh/D'uh were "rarely" used. However, the words On-trend/Trending, Internet, Cyberspace, Emoji, App, Goat, Basic, Bet, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, NOpe, Obvs ($M=3.38, SD=1.92$), Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, OMG, CYL, PM Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/RPFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IDK, IMYSM, TYL, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, SS, and BNW were used "occasionally" used. The words Vacay, and WERPA were used "sometimes" used.

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Further, when the participants were classified as to profession, the non-professionals “rarely” used the words Jeggings and Fo sho. The coined words Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Cyberspace, Goat, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas , FOMO , YOLO, LB, TBT, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM were “occasionally” used. While On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Swag, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Retweet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, IDK, TYL, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, PM , SS, and BNW were “sometimes” used. Internet, Goals (BBF goals/couple goals), Emoji, and App ($M=4.81, SD=2.02$) were used “frequently” used.

The professional participants “occasionally” used the coined words Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek ($M=3.05, SD=1.49$), Slay/Burn , Woke ($M=3.11, SD=1.63,$), Swag, Cyberspace, Bruh/Bro, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJ, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IDK, IMYSM, TYL, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW; “sometimes” used On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Goals(BBF goals/ Couple goals), Emoji, App, Vacay, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, OMG, OOTD, and FL; “frequently” used Internet.

When the participants were taken as to generation, the generation Z respondents “occasionally” used the coined words Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Cyberspace, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OOTD, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, and TYL; “sometimes” used On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Swag, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, OMG, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, IDK, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW; “frequently” used Internet, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), Emoji, and App; “rarely” used Jeggings; “occasionally” used Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Swag, Cyberspace, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO YOLO, LB, TBT, LMS, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, TYL, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, and BNW; “frequently” used On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, While OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, BRB, IDK, IMYSM, PM, and SS were used “sometimes” . However, Internet, Emoji, and App were used “frequently”.

When classified as to area of residence, the participants of Zone 1 “occasionally” used Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Epic, Swag, Cyberspace, Vacay, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OOTD, LMAO, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, and CTTO; “sometimes” used On-trend/ Trending, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), App, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, OMG, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMS, BRB, TBH, IDK, TYL, PM, SS, and BNW; “frequently” used Internet, and Emoji; “rarely” used Jeggings. For Zone 2 participantss, “occasionally” used Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Swag, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Boyf/Boyfie, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT, OOTD, FL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, TYL, CYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, PM, and BNW; “sometimes” used On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, OMG, NVM, LOL/ROFL, IDK, and SS; “frequently” used words were Internet, Cyberspace, and Emoji.

The participants of Zone 3 used the coined words Jeggings, Photobomb, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Cyberspace, Goat, Retweet, Fo sho, Perf, Noob/JOJO, Matchy-matchy, Yaaas, FOMO, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IDK, IMYSM, TYL, and CYL were used “occasionally”. The coined words On-trend/ Trending, Epic, Swag, Emoji, Vacay, Bruh/Bro, Basic, Bet, Netizens, Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie, Sis/Sissy, Nope, Obvs, Whatevs, Sesh, D’oh/D’uh, YOLO, LB, TBT, OMG, OOTD, FL, NVM, LOL/ROFL, LMAO, LMS, BRB, TBH, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, CTTO, and BNW were used “sometimes”. Lastly the coinages Internet, Goals (BBF goals/Couple goals), App, PM and SS were rated “frequently”.

When classified as to gender, there was a statistically significant difference in the following coinages: On trend/Trending, Internet, Goals (BBF goals/couplegoals), Cyberspace , Emoji , App , Fo Sho, Perf , Sis ,and TBT. A Post-hoc analysis showed significant difference between Male and Homosexual with On trend/Trending, Internet, Epic, Emoji , App , Fo Sho and Perf . Between Female and Homosexual the words were: On trend/Trending, Internet, Epic, Fo sho , and Perf , between Male and Female with Cyberspace and Sis/Sissy.

When classified as to area of residence, there was a statistically significant difference in the following coinages: Epic, App, LB, OMG, OOTD and NVM. A Post-hoc analysis showed significant difference in the following coinages: Between Zone 1 and Zone 2 the word was, Epic. For Zone 1 and 3 the words were: Epic, App, LB, OMG, NVM and OOTD. Between Zone 2 and 3 the words were: LB, OMG, OOTD, and NVM.

Further, when classified as to generation, there was no significant difference in the following coinages between generation Y and generation Z: Jeggings , Photobomb, On-trend/Trending, On fleek, Slay/Burn, Woke, Internet, Epic, Goals (BBF/Couple goals), Swag, Cyberspace, Emoji, App, Vacay , Bruh/Bro , Goat, Basic, Bet, Retweet, Netizens, Fo sho, Perf , Groufie, Boyf/Boyfie , Sis/Sissy , Obvs, LMS, Whatevs Sesh, Matchy-matchy , Yaaas, FOMO ,YOLO, LB, OOTD, FL, NVM , LOL/ROFL , LMAO, BRB, TBH, RN, IDK, IMYSM ,

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TYL, WERPA, TGIF, HMUA, PM and SS. While there was a significant difference on the following words Nope, Noob, TBT, OMG, CTTO and BNW.

When classified as to profession there was no significant difference in the following coinages between professional and non-professional: Photobomb , On-trend/Trending , On fleek , Slay/Burn , Woke, Internet , Epic, Cyberspace ,Vacay , Bruh/Bro, Goat ,Bet, Retweet, , Netizens, Fo sho, Perf, Groufie , Boyf/Boyfie , Sis/Sissy U=2091.000 Z=-0.-, Nope, Obvs ,LMS, Whatever, D’oh/D’uh , Matchy-matchy Yaaas, FOMO, YOLO, LB, TBT ,OMG,OOTD, LOL/ROFL, TBH, AMIRITE, RN, IDC, IMYSM, WERPA, TGIF and HMUA.

The following coined terminologies showed a significant difference: Goals (BBF/couple goals), Basic, Noob, NVM, LMAO, BRB, IDK, CYL, CTTO, PM, SS, and BNW.

Based on the results presented, it was found out that gender is a determinant of the use of new terminologies as upshot of coinage since there was a significant difference in the result. There were terminologies in which the female participants were most familiar with, while the male, homosexual, and lesbian participants were unfamiliar with. They mostly used the coined terminologies “occasionally”. With this, it can be concluded further that newly created terminologies could be necessary in communication to be understood easily but it is a case to case basis.

Furthermore, as to profession, since there was a significant difference, there were some professionals who did not yet fully embrace the use of new terminologies as upshot of coinage in this generation. On the other hand, non-professionals were accustomed with the newest trends since there was a significant difference on the list of coined terminologies.

C. Responses of the Participants as to How They Coin or Create New Terminologies

To triangulate the result of the study, the participants were asked on how did they coin or create new words for use. Some participants created words for things or situations that they cannot describe, by combining or adding words to make a difference from the ordinary words used and by imitation from other people especially celebrities from movies and television shows. Table 3 shows the responses.

TABLE 3. Responses of the Participants as to How They Coin or Create New Terminologies

Participants	Answers
A	<i>“I create a new term if I cannot describe a thing so I just come out with a word that is understandable but the message that I want to convey is still the same”</i>
B	<i>“By relating to the real situations and by combining/adding two words that makes the term exciting and interesting.”</i>
C	<i>“Combining two words or adding a syllable like ‘sureness’.”</i>
D	<i>“For me, it comes unexpectedly and sometimes, I utter words based on how I feel and sometimes based on the trends today.</i>
E	<i>“I create new terms by learning from the person who use it first.”</i>
F	<i>“I created new terms by adapting from what I have watched or read, then revise it.”</i>

D. Responses of the Participants as to How They Share New Terminologies among Themselves

The participants were further asked as to how they share the newly-coined or created terminologies among themselves. Some of them answered that they use their newly-created terminologies with their friends or age group through conversations, chatting, or in their social media account such as Facebook. Table 4 presents the responses.

TABLE 4. Responses of the Participants as to How They Share New Terminologies among Themselves

Participants	Answers
A	<i>“I share the new terms by using that new term to whom I communicate with”</i>
B	<i>“First let them guess the meaning. After that, if he/she cannot guess, I am giving another clue. Until he/she could guess the term.”</i>
C	<i>“Whenever we are having casual conversation among age group like hanging out or chatting</i>
D	<i>“I always use new terms when I’m with my friends and they</i>

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E	<i>happen to adapt and also use it.”</i> <i>“I shared new term by using it in my social media account and sometimes, verbally.</i>
F	<i>“I used the term to whom I communicate with or just post something on social media using that new term.”</i>

E. Response of the Participants as to How They Accept the New Terminologies as Part of Their Language

The participants were also asked as to how they accept the new terminologies as part of their language as millennials. Some of them answered that they accept the new terminologies by learning that language is dynamic, thus, can possibly change through time and generation. To add, because the millennials could understand the newly coined terminologies and feel happy to use them in their daily communication, by actual conversation or by social media interaction. Table 5 shows the responses.

TABLE 5. Response of the Participants as to How They Accept the New Terminologies as Part of Their Language

Participants	Answers
A	<i>“I accept the terminologies as part of my language by realizing that we (millennials) could still understand the change of terms for as long as it never affects our communication.”</i>
B	<i>“By accepting it as a whole because by creating new terminologies is already part of my behaviour.”</i>
C	<i>“By adopting the terminologies heard or seen on media or from other people, and using it, too.”</i>
D	<i>“I accept it because language is dynamic so learning how to live with it and always using it.”</i>
E	<i>“I accept it because language also improves and it’s part of the generation.”</i>
F	<i>“I accepted it because language is changing so we have no choice but to accept.”</i>

New terminologies as upshot of coinage could connect teachers as professionals to students, thus, classroom environment would become more interesting. As to generation, its own unique set of characteristics and norms is generally marked by an increased use and familiarity with communications, media, and digital technologies. There was a significant difference in the use of new terminologies among generation Y and generation Z. Most of the participants from generation Z were equipped of the online world compared with the generation Y. With this, it could be concluded that learning is eternal. Even at an older age, newly created terminologies could not be ignored because it would keep the bond with the younger generation.

Considering the area of residence, the result of the study might mean that participants of were aware and fond of sending, posting, and using social media accounts, but there were still residents who were not yet accustomed to the electronics-filled and increasingly online and socially-networked world. In conclusion, new terminologies are just coined through the globe even before, and people only have to be open-minded with the changes because it is a symbol of growth and development of a certain community.

The English vocabulary consists of more than one million words, including slang and dialect expressions and scientific and technical terms, many of which only came into use after the middle of the 20th century (Küpper, 2007). Matthews (in Nordquist, 2017) stressed that despite the exacerbated protests of the upholders of authority and tradition, a living language makes new words as these may be needed. This does not only bestows novel meanings upon old words but it borrows words from foreign tongues and it modifies its usages to gain directness and to achieve speed. Often these novelties are abhorrent, yet they may win acceptance if they approve themselves to the majority.

This irrepressible conflict between stability and mutation and between authority and independence can be observed at all epochs in the evolution of all languages, in Greek and in Latin in the past as well as in English and in French in the present.

On the other hand, Chevette (2003) stressed that, the millennials (born 1980-2000) are characterized by their dependence on technology, detachment from traditional institutions, optimism, and open-mindedness. It is no wonder that many people from different generations have a hard time understanding one another. As such, millennials are exerting their influence or new creations on the people and the world around them, as previous generations have done. According to Astrero (2017) the neologism in

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Philippine English is regarded by millennials as informal language. Further research is recommended to help identify the correct level of utilising Philippine English in an appropriate discourse.

Based on the interview, participants answered that they have created or coined new terminologies based on an experience or at an impulse and they share new terminologies with their friends and classmates or by social media. They accepted the changes in the language because they believe that language is dynamic and as millennials, they must consider this change as part of their generation.

The belief that a language ought to be 'fixt,' that is, made stable, or in other words, forbidden to modify itself in any way, was held by a host of scholars in the 17th and 18th centuries. They were more familiar with the dead languages, in which the vocabulary is closed and in which usage is petrified, than they were with the living languages, in which there is always incessant differentiation and unending extension. To 'fix' a living language finally is an idle dream, and if could be brought about it would be a dire calamity. Luckily language is never in the exclusive control of scholars; it does not belong to them alone, as they are often inclined to believe; it belongs to all who have it as a mother-tongue (Matthews in Nordquist, 2017).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The result of the study showed that gender is a determinant of the use of coined words, since there was a significant difference in the result of the use of coinages. There were words in which the female respondents were most familiar with. The male, homosexual, and lesbian respondents were unfamiliar with some coinages. They mostly used the coined words "occasionally". With this, it can be concluded further that newly created words can be necessary in communication to be understood easily but it's a case to case basis.

Furthermore, as to profession, since there was a significant difference, there were some professionals who did not yet fully embrace the use of coinages in today's world. On the other hand, the non-professionals were accustomed with the newest trends. There was a significant difference on the list of coinages.

In conclusion with this, coinages could connect teachers as professionals to students. Thus, classroom environment would become more interesting. As to generation, its own unique set of characteristics and norms generally marked by an increased use and familiarity with communications, media, and digital technologies. There was a significant difference in the use of coined words of the generation y and generation z. Most of the participants from generation Z were equipped of the online world compared to generation y. With this, it could be concluded that learning is eternal. Even at older age, newly created words could not be ignored because it would keep the bond towards younger generation.

Considering the residence, the result of the study might mean that the respondents of Zone 1, Zone 2 and Zone 3 were aware and fond of sending, posting, and using social media accounts, but there were still residents who were not accustomed yet with the electronics-filled and increasingly online and socially-networked world. In conclusion with this, coined words are just created through the globe even before. We only have to be open-minded with the changes that come in today's world because it's a symbol of growth.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

The millennials are recommended to participate actively in class and social activities so that they could understand that language is alive, thereby word creation predominantly exists in their generation.

Teachers may be aware of the current vocabulary of the millennials, specifically in the coinage of new terminologies. Further awareness and participation in activities of the younger generation could become a springboard in levelling up or coping with the demands of the newest trends in the society and shall be integrated in their lesson.

The researcher may submit a copy of the Glossary of New Terms or Compilation of Coined Words to the local libraries to bring awareness to the community. It is expected that the results may give a thorough explanation and better understanding on how language really works at the level of a rural community bound by latest technology in communication. In furtherance, the uniqueness of this study will be coined as a one-of-a-kind research that focuses on word creation.

Future researchers are recommended to consider this study for future research activities since this serves as a model in language research giving emphasis to the latest and current language development. They may also develop a more comprehensive study using other variables not used in this present study.

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